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Elephantology in Ancient Jain Literature and Culture

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Introduction

Elephants have played a prominent part in Eastern cultures from ancient times. In Asia, elephants have been used for transport, logging, war and religious purposes. They have fascinated humans for millennia and a vast literature related to their characteristics, diseases and their treatment developed in eastern cultures. The importance of elephant in war made their management very important for kings and a lot of literature on Elephant capture, training and Elephant husbandry came into existence in Sanskrit, the ancient language of India. All known texts agree in attributing knowledge of elephants to the Sage Pālakāpya¹. Apart from him, among the other ancient authorities referred to are Vīrasena, Bṛhaspati, Nīlakaṇṭha, Vyāsa, Nārada, Rājaputra and Vaiśampāyana. Indian poets have also described the behavior of Elephants in many of their works. However, there do exist still several elephant treatises in various manuscript repositories in India as well as in collections of various libraries outside India that are yet to be published and largely remain unknown.

Brief Overview of Earlier Sanskrit and Other Regional Elephant Treatises

Maharṣi Pālakāpya's treatise titled the '*Hastyāyurveda*'² is an elaborate text in the form of a discourse dealing extensively with elephant diseases and their remedies. It runs to about 20,000 or more

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verses and is in the form of a discourse between king Romapāda and Sage Pālakāpya and divided into four sections named *Mahārogasthāna*, *Kṣudrarogasthāna*, *Śalyasthāna* and *Uttarasthāna*. The *Agni Purāna*³, *Garuḍa Purāna*⁴ and *Kauṭilya Arthasāstra*⁵ also refer to Pālakāpya and draw some materials from his treatise. The '*Gajalakṣaṇa*'⁶ is in the form of a dialogue between king Nahuṣa and Br̥haspati mentioning different kinds of elephants and their characteristics. The '*Gajagrahaṇaprakāra*'⁷ of Nārāyaṇa Dīkṣita, an unknown author deals on role of elephants in work, wars and describes various methods of capturing wild elephants. Sage Vyāsa's '*Gajalakṣaṇa Chikitsa*'⁸, Sage Vaiśampāyana's '*Gajaśāstra*'⁹, Sage Nārada's '*Gaja Śikṣā*'¹⁰ and later texts like the '*Gajaśāstra*'¹¹ of Rāja Serfoji II (1798-1832 A.D.) from Tanjore, '*Mataṅgalīla*'¹² of Nīlakaṇṭha are other works on elephantology. Other descriptions of elephants in Sanskrit texts have been dealt in literature¹³.

Elephant Treatises by Jain Authors

Apart from the descriptions of elephants exclusively in Jain Canons, there exist some treatises on elephants by Jain authors that have not yet deserved much attention and lie deposited in various manuscript repositories in India as well as abroad. *Sīlānka*'s '*Chauppanamahāpuruṣacariya*'¹⁴ mentions a treatise on elephantology titled '*Hastīśāstra*' by *Bubbuha*. The '*Hastiparikṣā*'¹⁵ is a text in 1500 verses on elephants by Jain householder *Durlabharāja*, son of *Narasimha* and who served as minister of Chalukya King *Kumārāpāla* [1143 - 1174 A. D.]. It deals on their characteristics, duration of life, conception and their diseases. Another text namely the '*Gajaprabandha*' or *Gajaparikṣā*¹⁶ by Jain householder *Jinadāsa* who also served as minister of Chalukyan king *Kumārāpāla* was completed around 1158 c. A. D. The '*Gajathambha*'¹⁷ [*Hastirogachikitsā*] is an illustrated manuscript in the L. D. Institute of Indology, Gujarat that exclusively deals on diseases of elephants and their treatment. The authorship of the work is unknown. However in one folio it ends by stating.

iti śrī kokasārasāstra rasika sām̐pūma samāpta !

-- [Sam. 1747]

There is also a mention of *Āśāpuri Dhūpa* and *Surati Tamākhu* [Tobacco] in one folio. Interestingly it mentions several fevers that cause sufferings in elephants giving their characteristics and treatment as well as the causes. The '*Yaśastilakacampū*'¹⁸ of *Somadēva* also gives many details of elephants, their behavior and characteristics. It states that the committee of elephant experts appointed to examine and select the elephant for Yaśodhara's coronation was well versed in the treatises of Gautama, Pālakāpya, Yājñavalkya, Nārada and Rājaputra. The '*Mṛgapakṣīśāstra*'¹⁹ of *Hamsadēva*, a Jain author of the 13th c. A. D. mentions the characteristics of elephants. *Hamsadēva* also quotes the views of an earlier expert *Sunandaka* who authored a text on '*Gajaśāstra*'.

Elephants as Reflected in Jain Literature

Several ancient elephant treatises such as those by *Maharṣi* Pālakāpya and others deal on the characteristics of elephants, the stages of rut and anger (*Madāvastha*), their temperament depending on predominance of *doṣas* (fundamental bodily humours due to wind, phlegm and bile), behaviour of the elephants in the various regions for training purposes. Glimpses of such elephant behaviour are replete even in the ancient veterinary treatises available in Jain literature, the Jain canonical literature as well as in their *Kāvya*s. The Jain canonical texts consists of the 12 *Āṅgas*, 12 *Upāṅgas*, *Chedasūtras*, *Mūlasūtras* and *Chūlikasūtras* with their commentaries. The knowledge of elephants as described in ancient Jain literature may be studied under the following heads pertaining to various aspects as dealt in them.

[a] Origin of Elephants

Just as Sanskrit texts namely the twin texts '*Hastyāyurveda*' and *Gajaśāstra*²⁰ of sage Pālakāpya and the '*Mataṅgalīla*' of Nīlakaṇṭha describe the origin of elephants, similar descriptions are given in the '*Śivatattva Ratnākara*'²¹ [VII. 11. 4-8] of Keladi Basavarāja. It begins with mythical story of elephants having wings and flying in the sky. In course of time. they lost their wings due to a

curse of a sage and fell to earth as dealt in other Sanskrit elephant treatises. Interestingly, it states that Sage Kāśyapa had several wives of whom Krodha being the thirteenth had twelve daughters. Some of these daughters gave birth to elephants. Sage Mataṅga by his yogic powers pleased Lord Śiva by reciting *Sāmagāna* along with appropriate *Tālas* who then used the two half-shells of the Cosmic egg (*Brahmāṇḍa*) and reciting the *Sāmans* created the elephants known as '*Sāmajas*'. The '*Yaśastilakacampū*' of *Somadeva* also gives details of origin of elephants from the *Sāman* recitations of Lord *Brahma* (thus differing from traditional view as stated above) by which elephants took form from the two halves of the Cosmic egg just as the Sun took its birth during creation. The text also mentions that experts in *Gajaśāstra* and *Nīti* maintain that sages had cursed them to remain calm in royal palaces and follow the actions of Indra [III.190]

[b] Parts of the Body

The '*Hastyāyurveda*' [*Śalyasthāna, Pradeśajñānam*, Chap. 29] deals on the various parts of the elephant's body extensively that is also found in certain descriptions of Kannada *Kāvya*s. The earliest glimpses of such descriptions are found in *Pampa's Ādi Purāṇa*²² dated to 941 A.D. He terms the region between neck and chest of elephants as *Uromaṇi* in the text [12.56].

[c] Classification of Elephants

Just as Sanskrit treatises on elephants mention four classes of elephant, similar descriptions are found in Jain literature and *Kāvya*s. Sanskrit treatises speak of one type of classification having four classes of elephants such as *Dvija*, *Kṣatriya*, *Vaiśya* and *sūdra*. Another type of classification is based on their characteristics and is named as *Bhadra*, *Maṇḍalā*, *Mṛga* and *Miśra*. Jain Canons mention four species of elephant named as *Bhadra*, *Manda*, *Miya*, *Samkiṇṇa* that co-relate to *Bhadra*, *Maṇḍala*, *Mṛga* and *Miśra* classes found in Sanskrit elephant treatises. Their characteristics as gleaned from Jain canons are tabulated in **Tab. 1** although there are some variations in some texts.

Tab. 1 Classification of elephants in Jain Literature

Elephant class	Characteristics
<i>Bhadra</i>	Best and handsome having reddish brown eyes, long tail, lofty portions in the front. It sports in ponds and makes attacks by tusks.
<i>Maṇḍalā or Manda</i>	Slack and bulky, skin is irregular. It has tawny eyes similar to those of a lion. Have a large head, nails, strong tusks, sports in spring season and makes attack with trunk.
<i>Mṛga</i>	Feeble, timid and depressed in nature, having a soft neck thin skin, tusks and nail They sport in water and make attacks with lips.
<i>Miśra</i>	Lowest category, having mixture of characteristics, makes attack with whole body.

The '*Sthānāṅga Sūtra*'²³ [IV. 236-240] gives a description of the above four classes of elephants and also states that each of these have variations such as a mixture of the other classes based on the state of body and mind. The commentary to the '*Uttarādhyayanāsūtra*'²⁴ mentions that Dhavala elephants were whitish resembling the Moon, conch or *Kunda* [jasmine] flowers. They knocked down big trees. The Jain Prakrit epic '*Paumācariya*'²⁵ (PC) of *Vimalasūri* who belongs to *Svetāmbara* sect of Jains depicts life of Rāma according to Jain traditions. The elephant is known by several terms as spread out in the text such as *Haṭhī* [*Hastin* PC 2. 17]. *Māyāṅga* [*Mātaṅga*, PC 96.14], *Gaya* [*Gaya*, PC 3.61], *Kuñjara* [PC 2.111], *Kari* [*Karin*, PC 42.18] or *Vāraṇa* [PC 4.59]. The text also names certain elephants such as the '*Bhuvanālaṅkāra*' elephant of Rāvaṇa whose characteristics are described by Prahasta to Rāvaṇa [PC 8.215-217] which is seven *Hastas* [cubits] in height, nine *Hastas* in length and ten *Hastas* in circumference. It is the best type of

elephant. The divine elephant 'Airāvāṇa' [Erāvāṇa] is conveyance of Devendra [PC 2.38] and has four tusks [PC 71.3], The 'Hastiparīkṣā' of Jain householder Durlabharāja also deals on characteristics of elephants. The 'Gajaprabandha' or 'Gajaparīkṣā' by Jain householder Jinadāsa also deals on characteristics of elephants. The 'Mṛgapakṣisāstra' of Hamsadeva dated to 13th c. A. D. mention the characteristics of 13 types of elephants dwelling in the forests and termed as *Dantin*, *Dantavala*, *Hastin*, *Dvirada*, *Gaja*, *Bhadragaja*, *Manda*, *Mṛga*, *Saṅkīrṇa*, *Mataṅga*, *Padmin*, *Ibha*, *Stambherama* and *Hastinī*, [VI. 265-337] elaborately. The 'Yaśastilakacampū' [II.167-190] of Somadeva also gives several verses on tributes of praise being showered on elephants while they are presented on the eve of Yaśodhara's coronation. These include the praise of the elephant's prowess, its characteristics, how it seemed as if the earth began to breathe along with the celestial Ādiśeṣa when elephants heaved a sigh in the battle, praise of its speed stating that it is endowed with the fifth category of speed [similar to those of 5 kinds in horses] and also with the flow of rut [*Madalakṣmī*] and also praise of raising its trunk to the skies as if warning the Devas to protect their elephants. Somadeva also mentions several praises recited by keepers on occasion of sports of elephants witnessed by Yaśodhara as in the text [III.191-318]

[d] Elephant Forests

The 'Gajaśāstra' of Sage Pālakāpya speaks of sixteen principal elephant forests (*Gajavana*) that are divided into two main groups. The first group includes *Prācyā*, *Kaliṅga*, *Saurāṣṭra*, *Pañcanada*, *Daśāma*, *Āngareya*, *Aparānta* and *Chedikaruṣaka*. The descriptions of these forests as well as the characteristics of elephants found there have been elaborated in the 'Śivatattva Ratnākara' [VII.11.9-14] of Keladi Basavarāja and 'Mānasollāsa'²⁶ [*Viṃśati* II, Chap. III, 172-179] of Chalukyan king Someśvara and the 'Mṛgapakṣisāstra' of Hamsadeva.

The Jain text 'Piṇḍaniryukti'²⁷ [83] states that herds of elephants roamed in *Vindhya* forests and were caught in marshy reed jungles.

Special trainers [*Damagas*] trained them. The experts fed the elephant with green sugarcane, grass and barley [*Yavasa*]. Another Jain text namely the 'Āvaṣyakacūrṇi'²⁸ mentions that large herds of female elephants lived in the forests of *Rājagriha*.

The Jain text 'Nāyādhammakahāo'²⁹ (known also as *Jñātā Dharma Kathāṅga Sūtra*) also deals on characteristics of elephants. It mentions that princes were trained in controlling elephants. A wonderful description of forest life of elephants is found in the text. The 'Nāyādhammakahāo' portrays elephant behavior richly as in the narration of previous birth of Meghamuni as an elephant by Lord Mahāvīra. It states that in the forests of *Vaitadhyagiri* Mountains lived an elephant named Sumeruprabha that enjoyed the rivers, farms and plantations rich in bananas. Once when the forest caught fire, the elephant became restless seeing the other animals run hither -- thither, with their skin getting burnt due to the fire. The elephant's skin also got slightly burnt without food and water for several days it was pierced by the tusks of another young rogue elephant. Giving up its life, the elephant was reborn at the southern bank of Ganga river at the foot of *Vindhyagiri* Mountains. This elephant had four tusks known as Meruprabha had to undergo the same events of a forest fire. Having knowledge of its previous birth, it moved to a land eight miles away along with its herd. Due to the fear of fire, several animals had crowded in that place and a young rabbit clung to Meruprabha's leg. The elephant did not put down its leg in order to protect the creature, However as the fire died down, due to the prolonged strain in standing on three legs, Meruprabha died and took birth as Meghamuni, the son of king Srenik and queen Dharani.

The Jain text 'Vāsudevahimḍi'³⁰ (VH) of Sanghadāsa Gaṇi and Dharmadāsa Gaṇi, a Jaina version of Sanskrit '*Bṛhatkathā*' of Guṇāḍhya gives some interesting features of elephants, The 'Vāsudevahimḍi' mentions about prominent forests where elephants were found as well as those in regions such as *Kaliṅga*, *Kośala*, *Dasanna* and *Rāyagriha* as in VH [205].

[e] Stages of Life

Just as the ‘*Gajasāstra*’ of Sage Pālakāpya gives the various stages of life an elephant, one finds similar terms in the *Pārśvanātha Purāna*³¹ [4.109-112]-

*sale pota vikka sulalita kaḷabha javana kāntārūpa kalyāṇa
samujjvala yūtha vṛddha tera kṛśa
baḷahīnasthaviravṛddhamambivudaśeḷa II.*

These are described as ‘*Bāla*’ (1 year), ‘*Pota*’ (10 years), ‘*Vikka*’ (20 years), ‘*kaḷabha*’ (5 years), ‘*Javana*’ (30 years), ‘*kalyāṇa*’ (40 years), ‘*yūtha*’ (50 years) ‘*Vṛddha*’ (60 years). The ‘*Uttarādhyāyana Sūtra*’ has some interesting information on elephants. It refers to an elephant of 60 years of age.

[f] Clor and smell (odour of the Body of Elephants [*Varṇalakṣanam* and *Gandhalakṣanam*])

Several Ancient Indian elephant texts state that the color of elephants varies due to food intake, changes in *dośas* (fundamental bodily humours due to wind, phlegm and bile), country, class effects of planets and asterisms. They also state that one must examine the smell of the elephants’s mouth, eyes, temples, rut, breath, faeces, urine and water ejected from its trunk. Those having the odour of clarified butter, honey, earth, parched grains, curds (or buttermilk), milk, flowers like *Mālati* (*Jasminum glandiflorum*, L.), *Ketaki* (*Pandanus oforatisimus*, Roxb.) and *Jāti* (*Jasminum glandiflorum*, L.), sandal, *Vacha* (*Acorus calamus*, L.), Nectar, fragrant fruits are considered auspicious, Those elephants having the odour of blood, urine, faeces, puss, marrow, dead body, bird’s nest, garlic, ass, camel, boar, dog, goat and fishes are inauspicious and bring about distress and fear. The ‘*Śivatattva Ratnākara*’ [VII. II .113-122] of Keladi Basavarāja describes about elephants with fragrance [*Gandhahasti*] born of union of intoxicated male and female elephants. Their sweat, urine and excretion are fragrant like honey. The ‘*Vaḍḍārādhanē*’³², a Kannada text attributed to *Śivakoṭyāchārya* and dated to 10th c. A. D. in the context of narrating the story of *Sukuśalasvāmi* states that

king *Gandhabhañjana* received as a present a scented elephant in rut from king of Kalinga. He brought it under control through 32 elephant sports in a lake. The Jain text ‘*Āvaṣyakacūrṇi*’ mentions about *Gandhahastin* [a scented elephant] as the best species. It was the leader of the herd and attracted other elephants by scent.

[g] Whorls and marks on bodies of Elephants [*Āvartalakṣanam*]

Elephants are supposed to have several whorls and marks such as conch, earthen pot, fish, mirror, bull, lamp, sacrificial fire place, arrow, cowrie and umbrella that are auspicious. There also exist others that are considered inauspicious and bring misfortune. Whorls occur in six places of its body such as skin, root of tusks, tail, around the eyelashes, backbone regions, forehead and so on. These marks and whorls are elaborated in the descriptions of elephants given in the *Mṛgapakṣi śāstra*’ of Hamsadeva, ‘*Haṣtiparīkṣā*’ of *Durlabharāja* and the ‘*Gajaprabandha*’ or ‘*Gajaparīkṣā*’ of *Jinadāsa*.

[h] *Amśaka* (Partial Incarnation)

Ancient experts on elephantology state that *Anūka* is the name given to the character, gait, gesture and voice of other animals imitated by elephants or having these features based on its former state of existence as a heavenly being (based on its *Karma* of actions). Such features of partial incarnations in elephants have been elaborated in the ‘*Mānasollāsa*’ [*Vimśati* II, Chap. III, 324-281] of Chalukyan king Someśvara. The ‘*Śivatattva Ratnākara*’ [VIII.II.137-141] also describes the deities residing on the various limbs of the elephants. Several Jain texts such as the ‘*Nāyādhammakahāo*’ and ‘*Triṣaṣṭhiśalākāpuruṣacarita*’³³ (TSSPC) narrate the previous incarnations of elephants. The ‘*Triṣaṣṭhiśalākāpuruṣacarita*’ (TSSPC) is an elaborate narration of lives of 63 great persons in the Jain canons. It has several glimpses of elephants and their behaviour.

[i] Sound Production of Elephants

Several ancient texts dealing on Elephants speak of sound production in elephants. They discuss about the centres of sound production and also nature of the sound produced. According to the

'*Gajāsāstra*' of Sage *Pālakāpya* the sounds termed brahṁita comes from *Tālu* (palate) or *Gaṇḍa* (cheeks) or *Shira* (head), *Kaṇṭha* (throat), *Jihvā* (tongue), *Hasta* (trunk), *Udara* (belly), *śrota* (ears), *Garjitam* and *śamkha* from *Gala* (throat), *Meghanāda* from heart, *Hamsa* or *Dundubhi* from *Jihvā* (tongue), *karna* (ears), *Utkrośam* from *Gaṇḍa* (cheek), like tiger, lion or bull from head. Similarly other sounds produced by elephants as described in ancient Indian texts have been dealt in recent literature.³⁴ The '*Yaśatilakacampū*' of Somadeva states that the characteristics of rut, sounds, color of the body, its complexion, actions ['*Ceṣṭā*' such as omens of flapping its ears, trunk or tail] portray auspiciousness to the king and defeat of the enemy.

[j] Seasonal Behaviour

Indian poets laud the six different seasons in their works consisting of spring [*Vasanta*], summer [*Grīṣma*], rainy [*Varṣa*] Autumn [*Śarad*], Cold [*Hemanta*] and winter [*Śiśira*]. Likewise elephants are also thought to be subjected to seasonal variations in body and behavior. Sage *Pālakāpya*'s treatise '*Hastyāyurveda*' deals with such seasonal behavior in the *Kṣudra Roga Sthāna* [section on Minor diseases] in the *Thirteenth* chapter. Apart from these seasonal treatments given by *Hastyāyurveda*, the text also gives certain procedures that are to be practiced in all seasons for their welfare. These have been elaborated in detail in recent literature³⁵. *Glimpses* of seasonal behavior of elephants are also found in the '*Yaśatilakacampū*' of Somadeva. In describing the severity of winter cold, Somadeva states that the she-elephant languishes resting the trunk on the ground with her full breasts benumbed with cold.

bhūmisrastakarā kareṇuravaśakṣīrastanī tāmyati/ - [I.56]

Even at noon, elephants drink only the splashed water arising from waves in the banks of river.

Ahno ardhe api tarāṅgavāri kariṇo grhṇanti rodhaḥ / - [I.56]

In spring, male elephants caress their mates with mouthful of water.
gaṇḍūṣatoyairgajah śrṅgāraprasaraprasādihṛdayaḥ svām priyām sevate II - [III.442]

Elephants shake the trunks of old trees on banks of river *Śipra* [Chap. V]. The movements of elephant cubs are hampered by clusters of trees uprooted by violent gales [*kvacidbalānmūlitadrumākula kalabhapracāram*] [Chap. V]. In the rainy season Somadeva states that elephants are frightened by showers of ever falling rough hailstones hurled by the clouds--

meghodgīrṇapatatkathorakarakāsāratrasatsindhurepūraplāvitakū- apādapakulakṣubhyatsarītpāthasi || --[I.65]

The Jain *Apabrahṁsa* work titled '*Karkaṇḍacariu*'³⁶ of Kanakāmara Muni dated to 11th c. A. D. mentions that Padmāvati, queen of king Dadhivāhana, ruler of Champa city rode on an elephant which ran amok as it rained. The queen was carried into the forest for a long time and as the weather changed suddenly with the sun brightly shining the elephant entered the waters of a river to quench its thirst. Thus, the changes in weather appear to affect elephants. The Tamil epic '*Jivakacintāmaṇi*'³⁷ (JC) by a Jain author also has some interesting details of elephants. It mentions that prince Jivandhara allayed heat of sun from which a herd of elephants suffer by causing shower of rains. Elsewhere the text describes the royal elephant attacking Guṇamālā and her friend crying out for help. It further mentions that during summer, in a place where all the trees remain without any leaves on them, the male elephant in order to protect the she elephant from heat, covered her body with shadow of his body.

[k] Preternatural Behaviour of Elephants

Animals and birds live a life in the forest with complex behaviours that have astounded ancient men from immemorial times. They observed such behaviour and recorded them in the ancient literature that allows us to thus appreciate their observation skills. Even more surprising is the strange preternatural behavior of animals in presence of beings embodying supermatural power like sages. Such behavior has been reported in recent literature³⁸. Ancient Jain literature also offers us some glimpses into preternatural behaviour of elephants. The '*Āvaśyakacūrṇi*' mentions about an elephant '*Sechānaka*' falling into a cave. This incident is also elaborated in other Jain scriptures

and briefly summarized in the present context. The text mentions that large herds of she-elephants lived in forests of *Rājagṛha*. Among them, a male elephant on witnessing a young male playing around with female elephants suddenly remembered its earlier birth [*Jātismaraṇa Jñāna*] of being attacked and would crush and kill other male elephants. Thus subduing the herd, it became the king elephant and had constant observations on a female elephant that was pregnant. In order to protect the young one, the female elephant eloped by limping slowly, not catching up with the herd and at the time of delivery, it sought refuge in a hermitage. The young elephant was cared by the inmates of the hermitage. It watered the plants bringing water in pitchers or in its trunk and sprinkled them over it and attained the name '*Sechānaka*'. One while it was drinking water at a river, the rogue male elephant of the herd that had kept the female under observation attacked '*Sechānaka*' and was killed in the fight. The turn of events made '*Sechānaka*' bold as he became the herd and in its arrogance started destroying the hermitage where it grew. The inmates approached king Sreṇika of Magadha who had many sons like Ajātaśatru Kunik, Halla, Vihalla, Meghakumāra and Nandiśeṇa. Prince Nandiśeṇa, an expert in training and catching elephants stood in front of '*Sechānaka*'. The elephant also stood still by pondering the thoughts of his previous birth on seeing him. The prince and elephant tamers caught and tamed '*Sechānaka*'. The text states that Bhagavān Mahāvīra narrated the previous births of '*Sechānaka*' to prince Nandiśeṇa. The '*Nirayāvalika Sūtra*'³⁹ [1.23] states that Prince Vehalla ['Vihalla' according to other canons] was the younger brother of king Ajātaśatru. It also mentions the playful behavior of the elephant '*Sechānaka*' with the queens by placing them on its trunk, back, shoulders, neck, head, tusks and swinging them and also sprinkling water on them. Queen Padmāvati, the wife of prince Ajātaśatru Kunik out of envy saw the princes Halla and Vihalla perched on the elephant '*Sechānaka*' with their wives and the elephant playfully manipulating their ornaments. She reported the matter to Ajātaśatru Kunik and this led to the bitter battle between the princes. In order to attack Kunik's army the princes Halla and Vihalla resorted to guerilla-warfare with '*Sechānaka*' in the

night. Thus impending the forthcoming danger of a huge ditch of fire and being goaded by the princes with harsh words of being a treacherous animal, '*Sechānaka*' stepped ahead and gave up its life jumping into the pit. The text thus portrays an elephant endowed with knowledge of its previous birth [*Jātismaraṇa Jñāna*]. The '*Āvaśyakacūrṇi*' also states that earlier '*Sechānaka*' has gone to a river and was caught by a crocodile. It was rescued by a merchant's son. The '*Aupapātika Sūtra*'⁴⁰ also mentions about the incident of elephant '*Sechānaka*' sensing danger of ditch and stepping into pit of fire.

The '*Triṣaṣṭhiśalākāpurūṣacarita*' (TSSPC) text mentions that an elephant Gajapati of *Vindhyachala* mountain disturbed the meditation of sage Aravind who then by his *Jātismaraṇa Jñāna* narrated to the elephant about its earlier birth. The text states that the elephant became cool, sat meditating in its own way by looking at the sun for days, chanting *Namokar mantra* that was initiated to it and gave up its life. It was later attacked by a serpent when its legs got stuck in a lake and thus gave up its life.

The '*Sūtrakṛtāṅga Sūtra*'⁴¹ and its commentary mentions that a chained elephant saw ascetic Ardrākumār, thinking that if it was free of chains it could have paid homage. With noble thoughts in its mind, the chains broke by the spiritual influence of the ascetic and the elephant rushed towards Ardrākumār. The newly initiated disciples ran away. Elephant hermits in the forest confronted Ardrākumār complaining to him that they were not able to eat elephant meat. The ascetic pacified the hermits and asked them to attend Lord Mahāvīra's sermon [*Samavasaraṇa*]. Thus on being initiated, they gave up eating elephant meat. The '*Sūtrakṛtāṅga Sūtra*' thus portrays a class of people who relished elephant meat by killing them in the forests. The Jain text '*Nāyādhammakahāo*' also portrays the knowledge of previous births in elephants [*Jātismaraṇa Jñāna*] as in the case of elephant '*Meruprabha*' as stated earlier.

Some Jain Poets of Karnataka also mention preternatural behavior of elephants. The *Vardhamāna Purāṇa*⁴² [II.49] of Jināsena

Desavрати while describing the forest *Puṇḍarikinipura* where ascetic *Sagarasena* lived states that elephants, bear, tigers, lions and other animals shed their mutual enmity between them due to the spiritual influence of the sage. Similar descriptions of preternatural behavior are also found in Aggala's '*Chandraprabhā Purāṇa*'⁴³

[I] Musth and Ichor in Elephants

The '*Śivatattva Ratnākara*' [VII. 11 . 204] also mentions the eight types of ichor-

vāsā ca nāgaram śīthurgharmaśca madaśīkarau | cikkā mukhaśca kariṇām madanāmāni cāṣṭadha|

Even more interesting are the recipes given by the '*Mānasollāsa*' [Viṃśati IV, *Gajavāhyāvalivinoda*, III. 453-465] of Chalukyan king Someśvara to cause outflow and also increase of rut flow, create fragrance in the ichor and produce colors in the ichor of elephants that have been dealt in literature. Of these, the various states of intoxication in rutting elephants enumerated in ancient Indian texts, the descriptions in '*Yaśastilakacampū*' of Somadeva given by a military commander to prince *Yaśodhara* are excellent. These are as tabulated in Tab. 2.

Tab. 2. States of intoxication in Yaśastilaka campū

Names of Elephants	States of Intoxication
<i>Vasumatitilaka</i>	<i>Sañjātītilaka</i>
<i>Paṭṭavardhana</i>	<i>ādrakapolikā</i>
<i>Uddhatāṅkuśa</i>	<i>ādhonibandhinī</i>
<i>Parachakra Pramardana</i>	<i>Gandhacāriṇī</i>
<i>Ahitakulakālānala</i>	<i>Krodhinī</i>
<i>Charcharīvataṃśa</i>	<i>Ativartini</i>
<i>Vijayaśekhara</i>	<i>Sambhinnamadamaryāda</i>

Somadeva also enumerates different methods of treatment of rutting elephants-

*sottālabṛmhaṇasamcavyāstāstāramukhavardhanakaṭaśodhana
pratibhedanapravardhan avarṇakaroddīpanahāsanavinivarta
naprabhedamadopacāropadeśaviśārada ||*

The '*Uttarādhyāyanasūtra*' also mentions that an elephant was followed earlier by King *Padmaratha* of *Mithila* who had come for an elephant hunt. The elephant ran deep into the forest and attacked the chaste wife *Madanarekha* of prince *Yugabāhu* of *Sudarshanpur*. She saw the roaring mad elephant trying to attack her and was picked by it in the forest and thrown in the air like a ball. The text further states that she was rescued by a *Vidyādhara* in his *Vimāna*. The *Triṣaṣṭhiśalākapurūṣacarita*' (TSSPC) also mentions that '*Sechānaka*', elephant of King *śreṇik* broke its chain and rampaged the kingdom. When *Subhat*, a skilled trainer of elephants [according to the text] couldn't control him, the merchant *Dhanna* who was proficient in the art of '*Gajadāmini*', controlled the elephant. Jain texts also mention that King *Sreṇik* also was an expert in controlling mad elephants, calming them and tying them to a stable. He was rewarded for the act by king *Jitashatru*.

The Jain Prakrit epic '*Paumācariya*' (PC) of *Vimalasūri* states that training was given to princes to control elephants as in PC [8.218-223]. The Jain text '*Vāsudevahimḍi*' (VH) states that the royal paths of city of *Rāyagiha* [*Rājagrha*] were trodden by elephants with rut flowing from their temples acting as water spray. Kannada Jain literature such as *Aggala's 'Chandraprabhā Purāṇa'* [7.38] speaks of elephants that sport in the waters amidst the red lotuses sprinkling their pollen on the body. The '*Mallinātha Purāṇa*'⁴⁴ [10.90] describes about a ruddy elephant waving the trunk with the rut overflowing all over body and touching the eyes of another elephant pacifying its anger.

[m] Elephant Sports

Ancient Indian texts give various prescriptions to excite elephants for active participation in sports. Apart from this, elephants

were actively involved in sporting with other females as well as playing with their own herds in their natural habitats. Such elephant behaviour was seen predominantly when they were in musth and during spring seasons. Jain literature also gives us some excellent glimpses of such sporting behaviour. The *Mṛgapakṣiśāstra* of *Hamsadeva*, a Jain author of 13th c. A.D. offers some details on elephant sports. It states that elephants sport with their mates, feel happy by her sight, bring her everyday morsels of *Muñja* grass [*Erianthus munja*], sugarcane, plantains and lotus rhizomes [VI. 249-250]. They are also seen in water or on river banks engaged happily in love sports with females clasping them with their trunks for a long time [VI.241].

[n] Elephant Pregnancy and Calves

Descriptions of pregnancy, pre-natal and post natal care, foetus characteristics and difficulties in labour are well discussed in ancient Indian literature especially those pertaining to texts dealing on elephants. Elephants reproduce by natural birth or sometimes with difficult labour. In extreme cases, it may lead to caesarean sections to bring out the foetus. There may also be cases wherein the foetus may suffer constriction or be dead within the womb. The '*Hastyāyurveda*' [*Śalyasthāna, Garbhavakrānti*, Chap.8] begins with a lengthy query by King Romapāda to Sage Pālakāpya as to how females become pregnant, how does the foetus originate, in which months of pregnancy the bodily organs are formed, when does the young one come out as well as physical and mental conditions of the young one. Similar descriptions of pregnant females and behavior of calves are found in Jain literature. Guṇavarma II, a Jain Kannada poet in his '*Puṣpadanta Purāṇa*'⁴⁵ [924] dated to 1215 A.D. describes excellently the pregnancy of elephants. The '*Mallinātha Purāṇa*' [10.76] mentions an elephant calf sucking milk from its mother's breasts. *Aggala* in his '*Chandraprabhāpurāṇa*' has several interesting observations of elephant behavior. The text [9.77] mentions about a pregnant she-elephant unable to go to the river bed due to her heaviness. She keeps small steps and watches the river waters while the male elephant filling

its trunk with the waters sprayed it on the female. The Jain text '*Āvaśyakacūrṇī*' as stated earlier also mentions about the pregnant female elephant that moved away from the herd to protect the young one from the rogue tusker and gave birth to the elephant called '*Sechānaka*'. The *Mṛgapakṣiśāstra* of *Hamsadeva* also describes the growth and disposition of young elephants. The Jain Prakrit epic '*Paumācariya*' (PC) of *Vimalasūri* states that female elephant was called '*Kareṇu*' PC [42.18] or '*Kariṇī*' PC [80.53] and the young ones called '*kalaha*' or '*Kalabha*' PC [78.28].

[o] On the sensitivities by Goads and Weapons [*Veditalakṣaṇam*] and Taming Methods

Interestingly several Sanskrit elephant texts speak of characteristics of elephants based on their sensitivities to stimuli of the driver such as when being struck by weapons, pierced by goading instruments and so on. This sensitiveness is said to be five-fold. The Five-fold sensitiveness is said to be extreme (*Atyārtha*), shallow (*Uttāna*), deep (*Gambhīra*), conformable to meaning (*Anvartha*) and contrary to meaning (*Pratyārtha*). The '*Daśavaikālikasūtra*'⁴⁶ [II.10] mentions that mahouts used hooks [*Aṅkuśa*] to control elephants. Details of taming elephants are also given in the Jain text '*Vāsudevahimḍī*' (VH). *Vāsudeva* tames an elephant by hitting it at the back [VH. 221] and Dhammilla tames it by making it bend the head [VH.55]. The text also states that there were several methods of capturing and taming elephants. Of these one way was to decoy them with specially trained female elephants [*gaṇiyāgaṇiyāriu*] [VH.71], or alluring them with music of lyre or by other female elephants [VH II. 202] and also by driving them into rock cut depressions [VH. 201]. The '*Uttarādhyāyanasūtra*' [III.60] also alludes to Mūladeva who captivated a female elephant by playing *Vīṇā*. The '*Triṣaṣṭhiśalākāpuruṣacarita*' (TSSPC) also mentions that King Udayana followed an elephant with his assistants along with the playing of his *Ghoṣavatīvīṇā* and trapped it.

[p] Tusks of the Elephant

Some interesting observations of tusks of elephants are found

in Sanskrit literature. The art of cutting tusks of elephants is known as 'Kalpana' and the ivory obtained is used for making useful articles. The 'Kalpanāratna'⁴⁷ [IV.99.105a] of Śivamāra Bhūpāla gives excellent descriptions of elephant tusks. The text also gives the conditions and time period under which elephant tusks are to be cut. The 'Śivatattva Ratnākara' [VII. II. 149-154] also describes the details of sawing of elephant tusks, the seasons and time of operation, consequences or omens arising by chopping the tusks based on shapes of cleaved surface of tusks after carefully examining them. The 'Āvaṣyakacūrṇi' states that people killed elephants for the sake of ivory. Necklaces made from ivory were in use according to the 'Niśītha Cūrṇi'⁴⁸. The *Bhagavatīsūtra*⁴⁹ has a reference to ivory business [Dantavānija] stating that on the death of elephants, tusks and bones were used in ivory work. The 'Tilakamañjarī'⁵⁰ of Dhanapāla mentions several furnitures made of ivory of elephants such as royal ivory throne, ivory pavilion and ivory pegs to hang in sleeping chambers. The 'Bṛhatkalpabhāṣya'⁵¹ [1.2469] of Saṃghadāsa Gaṇi mentions about images made of ivory. The Jain text 'Pannavanā'⁵² [I.32] mentions that ivory workers are mentioned among important artisans. The 'Yaśastilakacampū' of Somadeva states that Yaśodhara also supervised the process of armouring the tusks of war elephants with sheaths of iron. Such methods of protecting the tusks are dealt elaborately in the elephant treatise 'Kalpanāratna' of Śivamāra Bhūpāla.

[q] Instruments and Ornamentation Associated with Elephants

The 'Matāṅgalīla' [XII.18] of Nīlakaṇṭha recognises four elephant hooks such as thunderbolt, half-Moon, nails and *Ketaka* thorn. It gives herbal mixtures to be applied to the tips of hooks to goad and control elephants as in the text [XII.22.24]. There are six different ways of wielding the hook. The *Uttarādhyāyanasūtra*' commentary mentions that elephants were tied to post [Ālana] the feet being secured with rope. The *Rāyapaseṇiya Sūtra*⁵³ mentions that the wooden seat on back of elephant was known as *Gilli*. The Jain text 'Vāsudevahimḍi' VH [203] states that king Abhaggasena of

Sālāguha received Vāsudeva outside the city and requested him to ride the elephant. Goaded by Vāsudeva the elephant moved with medium pace tied with golden ropes [*Kanagarajjupaḍibaddha*] and with two bells on its side. A carpet decorated with lotus creeper patterns was placed on its back. Caparisoned elephants with a carpet decorated with lotus creeper patterns was placed on its back. Caparisoned elephants with a fragrant pastes and girt with a rope at flanks [*Uppīliyakaccha*] are mentioned by the text. The 'Tilakamañjarī' of Dhanapāla mentions several ornaments for elephants such as *Pratimā* (ring fitted around the tips of tusks), *Nakṣatramālā* (Big necklace with many jewels corresponding to all asterisms in the Zodiac suspended on the temples of female elephant guarding the portals of royal palace) and *Kadalikā Kanaka Vaijayantī* (cloth woven with golden tinsels and having golden tinklers or strings strung along the borders). Elephants for royal possessions were decorated by painting their bodies. Prince Harivāhana's royal elephant named 'Amaravallabha' was besmeared by paste of white powder with temples and head being painted red with vermilion. Royal war elephant of *Vidhyādhara* Harivāhana was also painted white with sandal paste shining with tinges of powdered camphor particles and the temples and head painted red. The 'Bṛhatkathākośa'⁵⁴ of Hariśena mention that a necklace made of gems of elephants was one of the precious possessions of king Pūrṇacandra [78.148].

[r] War Elephants and Fights

Fights between elephants equal in physique, strength, age and class used to take place in their natural habitat as well as arranged by rulers for entertainments. Several poets also describe about elephant fights. The encyclopedic text namely the 'Mānasollāsa' of Chalukyan king Someśvara also describes elephant fights with exquisite details of the kinds of strokes made by tusks [*Vimśati* IV, *Gajavāhyāvalivivoda*, III.643-654]. These have been elaborated in recent literature⁵⁵.

The 'Bhagavatī Sūtra' mentions that elephants were used by kings in wars. The 'Bhagavatī Sūtra' [7.9.8] also mentions that Udāyin

and Bhūtānanda were two elephants of Ajātaśatru Kunik. The 'Uttarādhyāyanasūtra' commentary refers to warfare between Nami and Chandajasa over an elephant. The 'Āvaṣyakacūrṇi' states that Ajātaśatru Kunik led a bitter battle against the princes Halla and Vihalla who in turn resorted to guerilla-warfare with elephant 'Sechānaka' in the night. A reference to a battle between Kālkumāra and king Chetak in the text mentions that the former's army had 3000 elephants. The 'Āvaṣyakacūrṇi' also states that elephant *Nalagiri* was one of the four precious possessions of king Pajjoya. Likewise, elephant 'Bhadrāvati' belonged to Udayana who carried possessions of King Pajjoya. Likewise, elephant 'Bhadrāvati' belonged to Udayana who carried off Vāsavadatta. The 'Niśītha Sūtra' mentions about special experts [Ārohas] who rode elephants at the time of battle. The *Triṣaṣṭhiśalākāpuruṣacarita*' (TSSPC) in the context of narrating the story of King Udayana, states that the army of Avanti surrounded *Kauśāmbi* and tried to crash the gates of the city using mad elephants with rut overflowing from their temples. The text mentions that on the orders of a minister, a mechanized white elephant was made of wood by skilled artisans with a door in its belly. The driver seated inside it could control all the movements of the elephant including its trumpeting and other sounds. After the elephant was ready and surveyed by King Chandrapradyot, it was moved to the jungles bordering King Udayana's kingdom. King Udayana followed it with his assistants along with the playing of his *Ghoṣavatīvīṇā* and thus was trapped. He later escaped with Queen Vāsavadatta on the back of another male elephant to whose back four pitchers of urine of a female elephant were filled and thus dropped on the path to excite the smell of the following male elephant *Analagiri* of King Chandrapradyot. Deceiving the following elephant by this means Udayana reached *Kauśāmbi*. Jain texts also mention that elephant *Kajjalagiri* of King Nemiraja attacked the subjects. The king and elephant experts tried to capture it but it fled to the forest reaching the borders of Sudarshanpur. It was captured by King Chandrayash's

men who then led it into the royal stables. The text states that a big fight ensued between the King Chandrayash and Nemiraja. The latter then gave up the fight on reflecting the knowledge of his previous births. The Jain Prakrit epic *Paumācariya*' (PC) of *Vimalasūri* states that tame elephants were used in war PC [4.59] and PC [12.113] and were maintained in stables (*Hastisālā*) as in PC [80.63]. Kings prefer to ride elephants in battle as in PC [10.6] and PC [10.64] or in public processions PC [3.2]. Elsewhere the number of elephants in each division of the army such as *Paṅkti*, *Senā*, *Senāmukha*, *Gulma*, *Vālma*, *Vāhinī*, *Prtanā*, *Chamū*, *Anikinī* and *Akṣauhiṇī* is mentioned as in PC [56.3-9]. Elephants used to have fight with other elephants in wars stated in PC [6.182]. When cities were looted excellent elephants were carried away as stated in PC [8.66]. The *Bhadrabāhu Saṁhitā*⁶ (BBS) of Jain *Bhikṣu* Bhadrabāhu dated prior to *Bṛhatsaṁhitā* of Varāhamihira gives several predictions based on the actions and characteristics of elephants. It states that if an elephant sleeps with right foot towards west and does not eat food, then death of commander-in-chief occurs as stated in BBS [XIII.158]-

*sausupyante yadā nāgaḥ paścimaścaraṇastathā | senāpativadhān
vidyād yadā' nnaṁ ca na bhujate | |*

If it does not eat food, water, grass and rejects then destruction of army occurs as stated in the text BBS [XIII. 159]--

*yadānnaṁ pādavārīm vā nābhinandanti hastinaḥ | yasyām tasyām
tu senāyāmacirādvadhānādiṣet | |*

It a king sees blood drops on the face of an elephant during a march, he suffers defeat BBS [XIII. 162]. If an elephant trumpets continuously, it forebodes victory BBS [XIII. 165]. If marks [termed *Puṣpa's*] in colors of yellow, red or white occur on the front portion of tusks, then it forebodes victory BBS [XIII.166]--

*puṣpāṣi pītaraktāni śuklāni ca yadā gajāḥ | abhyantarāgradanteṣu
darśayanti yadā jayam | |*

In an army if an elephant pulls the feet of another or digs the earth by its feet, the enemy attacks the king BBS [XIII. 168]. The *Bhadrabāhu Saṁhitā* BBS [XIII. 169] also states that in the context of mad elephants or those elephants that are in rut get distressed or in which the rutty elephant herds also do not attain rut, then the king or minister will be killed.

*mattā yatra vipadyante na mādyante ca yojitāḥ | nāgāstatra vadho
rājño mahā' mātīyasya vā bhavet ||*

The predictions related to elephant action during a march of a king [*Yātrā*] are also given by the text as tabulated in Tab. 3.

**Tab. 3 Predictions of elephants related to march of a king in
Bhadrabāhu Saṁhitā**

Actions of Elephants during March	Prediction of the Omens
Elephant lifts trunk up and makes sound	Fulfillment of desires
Tusks are broken.	Fear, distress and death
An elephant trumpets and a rutty elephant comes in front.	Success of <i>Yātrā</i>
Elephant destroys wrestlers and comes running forward	Defeat, distress, and destruction of wealth.
Sudden death of elephants	Arrival of another ruler for state.

The '*Tilakamañjarī*' of *Dhanapāla* also mentions the use of elephants for war purposes. The '*Bṛhatkathakośa*' of Hariśena mentions that subduing royal elephants was considered an act of bravery. Arkakīrti and Hariṣeṇa are mentioned as skilled elephant controllers who defeated elephant drivers and subdued royal elephants [*Rājahastin*]. Kannada literature by some Jain poets also depicts glimpses of war elephants. The '*Neminātha Purāṇa*'⁵⁷ of Mahābalakavi (1254 c. A.D.) describes the elephants fight raising their trunks, piercing their tusks against one another, pushing and pulling each other.

[s] Mahout Communications

Just as the '*Matāṅgalīla*' [XII.8-16] of Nīlakaṇṭha recognises several commands given by mahouts to instruct and control elephants, similarly the '*Mānasollāsa*' [*Viṁśati* II, Chap. III.290-306] of Chalukyan king Someśvara also describes several commands, words, striking and gooding methods to train and control elephants. The '*Yaśastilakacampu*' of Somadeva states that Yaśodhara was proficient in elephant lore like Romapāda, king of Aṅga. He mentions that Yaśodhara with stick in hand, trains elephants and addresses it by various verses and terms like.

he he hala divyasāmaja mātrāsataṁ tiṣṭha tiṣṭha |

Another verse describing the instructions to elephant states--

*gātraistiṣṭha samaiḥ puronakhasamaṁ hastaṁ nidhehi kṣitau
dṛṣṭim dehi karāgrataḥ sthīramanāḥ karṇau gajāśleṣaya | vālaṁ
dhāraya |*

“Stand with thy limbs in equipoise. Place trunk on ground on a level with claws. Fix thy look on tip of trunk. O' Tusker hold thy ears motionless with a steady mind. Move not the tail”.

-- [III. 282]

Similar methods of taming elephants by hitting it at various spots on the body are given in the Jain text '*Vāsudevahimḍi*'.

[t] Elephant Diseases

The '*Hastyāyurveda*' of *Maharṣi Pālakāpya* deals on Elephant diseases and their remedies extensively. The four sections named *Mahārogasthāna*, *Kṣudrarogasthāna*, *Śalyasthāna* and *Uttarasthāna* deal on all type of diseases that are elaborated in literature. The *Kṣudrarogasthāna*, [Chp. 43] of the text devotes an entire chapter to treatment of old age of Elephants and their daily regimen. Some diseases of elephants as well as their treatment are treated in the '*Mānasollāsa*' [*Viṁśati* II, *Bālādhyāya* VI.628-677] of Chalukyan king Someśvara. Glimpses of treatment of elephant diseases in Jain literature are rare although the troubles faced by elephants are described

in various contexts. The '*Yaśastilakacampū*' of Somadeva [III.188] also states that a king should arrange for bath, drink and food for elephants without which he himself should not have his own.

asnānapānabhukteṣu tatkriyaḥ syānnayatsvayam ||

Diseases of elephants treated by Pālakāpya were also aware to Jain scholars as these are well illustrated partially in the text of '*Gajathambha*' that exclusively deals on diseases of elephants and their treatment. The text mentions several fevers that causes sufferings in elephants giving their characteristics and treatment as well the causes. These fevers namely *Bhramarajvararoga*, *Vikramasādhi*, *Adhbhutajvara*, *Ragatāsajvara* and *Viśādhajvara* and are illustrated in the manuscript. These should be studied along with the '*Pākala*' fevers that are described by sage Pālakāpya in his '*Hastyāyurveda*' text.

[u] Omens Related to Elephants

Several Jain scriptures mention the omens arising from elephants in various contexts. The Jain Prakrit epic '*Paumācariya*' (PC) of *Vimalasūri* states that during Rāvaṇa's final march to the battlefield elephants trumpeted frightfully striking the earth with their trunks as in PC [69.47-53] foreboding his defeat of death. The elephant was regarded to be auspicious on occasion of marriage as in PC [10.8]. The text also states that the queens Marudevi and Padmāvati at the time of conceiving Ṛṣabha and Munisuvrata saw elephant as one among fourteen dreams PC [21.1]. The '*Uttarādhyāyanasūtra*' also states that elephant was seen among the fourteen dreams by queen Śivādevi before giving birth to *Bhagavān* Neminātha. Jain texts like the commentary *Doghaṭṭī ṭikā*⁵⁸ on '*Upadeśamālā*' by Ratnaprabhāsūri (1181 c. A. D.) state that King Chandragupta and *Ācārya* Chāṇakya met *Ācārya* Bhadrabāhu. The King questioned about meaning of strange dreams seen by him to which Bhadrabāhu interpreted the meaning of these dreams. Of these the eleventh dream of a monkey jumping on the back of divine elephant Airāvata meant that lower caste and fickle minded people would rule the state. The sixteenth dream of black elephants coming to an arena to fight but retreating

meant that weather cycles would get disturbed in the future with black clouds [like elephants] of monsoon approach but scattering without rain in time of need.

Thus, one finds rich descriptions of Elephantology in Jain Scriptures Research into further unexplored texts and their associated commentaries would give us a complete picture of *Gajaśāstra* according to these Jain authors.

Conclusions

Glimpses of elephant behavior are replete in many of the available elephantology treatises. The descriptions of Sage Pālakāpya's text are so exquisite that they inform us about the behavior, characteristics, diseases and their treatment and are treated elaborately in his '*Hastyāyuroeda*' text. Sage Pālakāpya's '*Gajaśāstram*' is available in various Sanskrit as well as vernacular recession and deals on the various aspects. Elephants are also described in ancient Jain literature outlining various aspects. Some of these have been gleaned from Sanskrit as well as vernacular recessions and deals on the various aspects. Elephants are also described in ancient Jain literature outlining various aspects. Some of these have been gleaned from Sanskrit treatises while some are the descriptions of native Jain scholars. Several ancient manuscripts on elephants in Jain literature have not yet been critically edited and the information in these texts in yet to be compared with other earlier texts. Existing descriptions in Jain literature enriches our understanding of the subject of elephants mainly on aspects of its characteristic features like color, whorls, smell, complexion, sensitivity, classification of elephants, age, feeding habits, diseases, treatment capturing methods and so on. Interdisciplinary research supported by Modern field studies may allow one to admire these ancient observations of elephants made in Jain literature and also offer us new perspectives on their contributions. Jain canons also throw some interesting details on elephant behavior not found in other treatises on elephant lore. These include the descriptions of the '*Uttarādhyādhyanasūtra*', *Bhadrabāhu Samhitā*,

Yaśastilakacampū’ of Somadeva, ‘*Āvaśyakachūrṇi*’, ‘*Triṣaṣṭhiśalākāpurūṣacarita*’ (TSSPC) and several Jain works and epics. The predictions pertaining to actions of elephants are found in *Paumācariya*’ (PC) of Vimalasūri, *Bhadrabāhu Saṁhitā* and ‘*Vāsudevahimṇi*’. Jain texts also mention several kings, princes and experts well versed in controlling elephants. Aspects of war elephant seasonal behaviour, Art of armouring elephant tusks or crafting skilled mechanical elephants to elude the enemy are also mentioned in Jain texts. The ‘*Yaśastilakacampū*’ of Somadeva mentions that experts well versed in earlier treatises on elephants used to examine and select them for royal purposes. The authorities quoted by Somadeva are also found in sage Pālakāpya’s text thus allowing one to know that Jain traditions were aware of these texts. The ‘*Vāsudevahimṇi*’ mentions certain methods of capturing elephants that are mentioned also by the *Gajagrahaṇaprakāra*’ of Nārāyaṇa Dīkṣita. Some of the diseases mentioned by Pālakāpya’s text are also known to Jain scholars as illustrated in the ‘*Gajathambha*’. Research on elephant diseases as well as other aspects as gleaned from various other Jain texts such as unpublished *Kāvya*s, *Champū* literature and commentaries, folk Ballads and orally transmitted knowledge needs to be documented. A Thorough search for other elephant texts surviving in manuscript form in various manuscript repositories and private collections needs to be carried out and preserved for future generations. This will allow one to research Elephantology aspects according to the Jains and thus promote their conservation by practically using their knowledge.

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Comparative study of Quantum Mechanical Behaviour in the light of Jain Philosophy

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1. Introduction

When philosophical ideas associated with science are dragged into another field, they are usually completely distorted. Therefore we shall confine our remarks as much as possible to some part of Jain philosophy and as well as material aspect and behaviour regarding quantum physics itself. Quantum Physics sometimes dealing with the behaviour of matter and light on the atomic and sub-atomic scale. It attempts to describe and account for the properties of molecules and atoms and their constituents. The most interesting aspect is the idea of the wave-particle duality, Niels Bohr's complementarity principle, uncertainty principle etc. On the other hand, the Jaina philosophy of *anekāntavāda*, particularly *syādvāda* points out the similarity with modern science like Niels Bohr's Principle of complementarity, uncertainty principle. In Jain philosophy, matter has been analysed on the basis of its conception as a permanent substance possessing infinite qualities and modes with unique notions about it as physical science. In this context it would be studied comparatively between some of quantum mechanical aspect and Jaina philosophy. To begin with the concept of matter by throwing light on Jaina conception of Reality- *Dravya* (substance), *guṇa* (quality) and *pariyāya* (mode) and

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